

IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE USING FINANCIAL SUPPORT IN FOOD SECURITY OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the assessment of the state of the food problem and ways to solve it in the XXI century, determining the economic importance of the industry. Assessing the importance of the use of innovative technologies and the effective use of the achievements of genetics and breeding to increase the productivity of animal husbandry.*

Keywords: *food security, climate change, production and consumption, labor efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

It is important to suggest that agriculture is the most extensive and vital sector of the country, providing the population with food, raw materials for the food and light industries. Throughout all social and societal formations, food production has always been and continues to be the primary condition for the life of direct producers. The agricultural complex unites three spheres of public production, such as:

1. A set of heavy industries that produce means of production for agriculture and support industrialization;
2. Agriculture itself, which produces food and raw materials for industrial processing;
3. The light and food industries, which process about 75% of the country's agricultural output.

At present time the sector depends on the introduction of innovative technologies in agriculture, as the level and pace of agricultural development directly affect the development of the food industry and, to a significant extent, the light industry. Along with them, an integral part of agriculture within the agro-industrial complex is its infrastructure, which serves as the economic and financial foundation of the process that delivers products to the consumer. This includes the sector serving all industries, such as transportation, packaging production, storage and processing of products, wholesale and retail trade [1].

Definitely, as infrastructure in public production is divided into two interconnected forms: the first is the production form in agriculture, which includes essential subdivisions such as organizational support for production (such as procurement, transportation, storage, and sales of products, etc.); and the second is the social form, which is responsible for housing, education, healthcare, as well as cultural leisure and household services for the population. All of the above forms depend on the planned development of the agricultural sector, whose efficiency is determined by the innovative and technological development of production, material well-being, and the culture of the nation [2].

SOURCE DATA AND RESEARCH METHODS

The expanded use of innovative technologies in agriculture is ensured in accordance with the existing system of objective and subjective economic laws, adhering to the principles of

systematic and rational development of the social factors of labor, value, distribution, and consumption, as well as the proper balance between the social and personal interests of employees in the agricultural sector [3].

What is more important, with the development of technological innovation and the effective use of advances in genetics and breeding to increase livestock productivity, coupled with a deeper understanding and application of the laws of nature, particularly, the biology of living organisms such as plants and animals - the positive impact of humans on many environmental processes inevitably increases. This is achieved by using favorable conditions to renew and expand the cycles of life for plant and animal organisms. This approach is particularly useful in regions with challenging climatic conditions, influencing the development of animal husbandry as a whole [4]. In areas where industrial production methods are developed, such as poultry farms, livestock complexes, and the production of vegetables in protected soil, seasonality in production is nearly nonexistent, improving labor profitability and internal production, thereby contributing to the country's food security [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methodology for collecting and studying facts plays a crucial role in scientific research on agriculture, especially in the presence of various forms of farming such as clusters, farms, inter-farm enterprises, organizations, and subsidiary farms of private owners. Data on individual farms may not be indicative for the corresponding sector, let alone for agriculture as a whole, even within districts. Therefore, alongside the study of advanced innovative technologies and their application, there must be an interconnected approach with the economic and financial processes in agriculture, considering the economic-geographical zones of the country.

Based on the above-mentioned ideas, the following methods can be suggested for the development of agriculture, which have been classic and consistent for centuries:

- Monographic method, which involves examining and studying individual farms, different technological processes, the state of certain industries, and achievements from leading clusters and farms with the aim of identifying new and progressive elements for widespread adoption and application in practice.
- Production-analytical method, which can be used to study production based on extensive data from both the entire farm and its individual sectors. This method aims to uncover economic, organizational, agro-zootechnical, and other factors that influence the increase in production efficiency, and to generalize and substantiate new innovative phenomena that contribute to the further advancement and development of agriculture.
- Financial-economic method, based on the study of large-scale data over a three-year period, such as annual reports from clusters, farms, private entrepreneurs, etc., through the use of various groupings and factors that determine results (for example, intensification, concentration, specialization, mechanization levels, labor efficiency over a specific period, the size and structure of livestock, the provision of feed to animals), the cost of production and its structure, the degree of labor resources, and labor productivity. This method also supports the formation of measures for further development and improving production efficiency. The use of the economic-statistical method allows establishing correlation relationships between factors and results, based on which scientifically grounded proposals for improving agricultural production efficiency can be developed.

- The calculation-design method can be used in forward planning, when developing different solution options and tasks with justification of the most economically effective option. This method ensures the acceleration of national production development, providing food security through modern and prospective production technologies, considering the latest achievements in science and advanced practices in agriculture at both local and global levels of the country.

- The balance method, in accordance with the requirements of the law of systematic proportional development, is applied to justify the proportions in the development of various sectors of agriculture and related sectors within the agro-industrial complex. It can contribute to the justification of specialization and concentration of production based on inter-farm cooperation and agro-industrial integration, with the goal of achieving effective agricultural development and a proper balance between sectors.

- The abstract-logical method supports the historical study of reality and the theoretical generalization of processes that determine the prospective development and effectiveness of national production, guided by financial and economic laws.

- The financial-mathematical method is recommended for modernizing financial technologies and new payment systems that accelerate the process of financial credit policy in regions, aimed at improving and reducing poverty. It involves significant investments in social protection and agricultural infrastructure, ensuring the purchasing power of money. The impact of changes in the payment structure in agriculture affects the velocity of money circulation, as price shifts alter the demand for money, which in turn changes the amount of money needed for circulation. This tactic is actively used by modern monetarists when constructing the theory of demand for money. It would be beneficial to apply it consistently in the sector, as it would help ensure a stable capital supply for the continuous cycle of agricultural reproduction.

- The experimental method involves the development of specific proposals and methods for the widespread implementation of these innovations into new production processes.

CONCLUSION

The main task of agricultural economics is to contribute to the further growth and stability of public production, ensuring more complete satisfaction of the population's needs for food and raw materials for industry, while creating necessary state reserves of agricultural products. The rise of agriculture requires increasing the economic knowledge of agricultural leaders and specialists, promoting conscious and highly productive activities among students, utilizing rational material labor, resources, and scientifically justified production methods to help the development of the sector at all stages of agriculture in the country.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the agricultural economic sector should facilitate the establishment of proper economic relations between urban and rural areas, and between industry and agriculture, based on a strict understanding of the law of value within the system of rational and sustainable management. An improved system for the procurement of agricultural products, scientifically justified purchasing prices, and the state-sponsored work (such as land reclamation, land planning, protective forestry, and the construction of roads with quality materials) will significantly improve economic relations between clusters, farmers, and the state. These initiatives create additional material incentives to accelerate the pace of agricultural production development.

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